

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2024 Annual Report

Volume 3, Program Foundation Development and Outreach

A Program researcher talking with a wetland property manager next to a water level control structure at an H2Ohio wetland Project. Photo credit: Olivia Schloegel

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This volume (Volume 3) of the 2024 Annual Report highlights accomplishments related to program development, workforce and student training, and outreach and engagement of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program.

Note: The data and management summaries contained in this report are provisional. Every effort has been made to ensure their correctness. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is supported by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, the Ohio Water Development Authority, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency’s Great Lakes Restoration Initiative, and the Ohio Department of Higher Education’s Harmful Algal Bloom Research Initiative Program. The information, findings, and conclusions in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the funding organizations. Any use of trade, product, or firm names is for descriptive purposes only and does not imply endorsement by the State of Ohio or U.S. Government. Contact the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program prior to using these data and before citing research and management findings.

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Program Accomplishments Overview

Investments in the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program support many non-data related outcomes and benefits, including:

- outreach and engagement to cultivate relationships among researchers, agency personnel, and conservation partners;
- advancing scientific research through development of standardized protocols and presenting results in academic conferences and other settings; and
- workforce development of analytical, communication, and technical skills among early- and mid-career professionals.

To align with the quarterly progress reports, Program Accomplishments are compiled by calendar year (January 1, 2024–December 31, 2024).

Outreach and Engagement

In alignment with the Program’s guiding principles of “A Community of Researchers, Professionals, and Partners” and “Learning by Doing in an Adaptive Framework,” the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program researchers work with agency staff, restoration professionals, and wetland property managers year-round. Restoration professionals who design and build H2Ohio Projects often provide invaluable knowledge about restoration approaches and Project features. Wetland property managers share and help document hydrologic management and other on-the-ground changes, which the Monitoring Program can consider in assessment of wetland water quality nutrient function. Frequent back-and-forth communication among stakeholders and researchers is a vital aspect of the Program. For example, feedback shared by agency staff, restoration professionals, and wetland property managers at the 2024 workshop was applied toward a suite of case study overviews summarizing results from specific Projects. Likewise, a small group (five people) of agency staff and restoration professionals met quarterly, including a meeting to develop a list of key questions to frame the 2024 public webinar. Communication products are on the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network website at this direct link: <https://lakeerieandaquaticresearch.org/research/learn-initiatives/h2ohio-wmp/h2ohio-webinars-and-outreach-materials-archive/>

2024 Workshop

At the 2024 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Workshop’s Partner Day, approximately 70 Program researchers, Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR) staff members, and restoration professionals gathered to hear informational presentations on drainage area estimation, hydrologic flow path identification, sensor network accomplishments, and tradeoffs of different nutrient budget approaches. The goals of the event were to share research updates, highlight engagement plans, and integrate multi-source data. An unstructured networking lunch allowed connections to form among individuals across wetland Projects and institutions. Participants helped improve communication products, like the 2023 Project overview case study

of Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area. The semi-structured feedback gathered from partners at the Workshop strengthened 2024 overview case studies, making them more relevant and useful in communicating current results. Overall, the workshop strengthened the Program's reporting ability and informed future monitoring efforts.

Two-Page Overview Case Studies

At the request of the ODNR, four case studies were completed in collaboration between H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program researchers and Ohio Sea Grant communication staff. The overviews outline and communicate preliminary monitoring results from Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland, Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration, Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection, and Magee Marsh/Turtle Bay Floodplain Reconnection. The case studies were informed by insights on detail, uncertainty, and decision-making needs gathered through discussions of the 2023 Burntwood-Langenkamp case study at the 2024 Workshop.

2024 Webinar

The 2024 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Annual Update webinar was held on December 4, 2024. Invitations were sent to the Ohio Sea Grant mailing list, Ohio Department of Natural Resource management staff, and various stakeholders. The target audience was professionals who make decisions regarding wetland restoration and management so that the webinar could amplify the importance of continued dialogue among researchers, agency staff, and wetland practitioners. Program Research Lead Lauren Kinsman-Costello presented an overview of Program accomplishments. Kenny Anderson, a post-doc working on a Great Lakes Research Initiative-supported sensor project Post-doc Seventy-two people attended the 2024 webinar, and as of April 14, 2025, there have been approximately 450 online views.

Outreach and Engagement Personnel

In August 2024, the Program added and filled a new Outreach and Engagement Coordinator position to contribute to additional outreach communication products and expand data collection, specifically through Project partner and citizen (participatory) science sampling. The early accomplishments for this position from September 2024 to December 2024 include:

- re-catalyzing and expanding volunteer-collected data through Crowd Hydrology (crowd-sourced water level gauge measurements) at the Oakwoods Restoration Project East and West,
- co-drafting an affiliate research agreement for data collection and sharing,
- scoping networking potential with Cleveland Water Alliance and Lake Erie Volunteer Science Network
- participating in the International Joint Commission's Charting the Future of Great Lakes Participatory Science workshop, providing feedback on framework and planning of potential resource hub, and

- planning a participatory science presentation and interactive activity at Partner Day of the 2025 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Workshop.

Advisory Group

At Partner Day of the 2024 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Workshop, four partners (three restoration professionals and one state agency staff member) signed up for an advisory group. The goal of the group was initially to continue productive conversation started at the workshop regarding the Monitoring Program’s communication products and their relevance to management audiences. The group met virtually four times in 2024 (March, May, August, October), in which the group had a comprehensive discussion on two-page case study usefulness and audience. Additionally, the group documented strengths and limitations of the 2023 Monitoring Program Annual Report, including how wetland features and common wetland restoration design attributes can be better amplified in Monitoring Program sampling schemes and data communication. The group also helped build a list of key questions to frame the 2024 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program public webinar.

Collectively, the emergent themes from the quarterly advisory group meetings included:

- importance of clarifying audience for a given communication product,
- providing parallel structure and at-a-glance data synthesis where possible in reporting,
- the paradigm shift from habitat-based restoration toward nutrient-based restoration while operating within respective missions of partner organizations, and
- information access at different stages of wetland proposal, creation, and monitoring.

Monitoring Protocol Development

In alignment with the Monitoring Program’s commitment to “Responsible, Open, and Sound Science” and “Building a Foundation for Long-term Monitoring,” H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program researchers formalized and finalized Program-wide monitoring protocols, updated the Program’s guiding framework document, provided additional voluntary support to the Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR) H2Ohio wetland restoration proposal review process, and engaged with the broader public and professional communities through various presentations, publications, and meetings.

Monitoring Protocols

Monitoring Program researchers compiled over 20 field sampling and lab analysis protocols to ensure data quality and reproducibility. The protocols, informed by previous years of initial monitoring, are available upon request via h2ohiowetlands@kent.edu.

Updated Monitoring Program Framework

The H2Ohio WMP Monitoring Framework¹ was updated and published on Open Science Framework in September 2024 and can be found at this direct link: <https://osf.io/z5tm3>. The updated framework more accurately reflects feasible Program workflows than the original framework, integrates initial lessons learned about Program structure, and omits redundant content that was moved to Monitoring Program protocol documents.

Researchers' Volunteer Review of H2Ohio Proposals

Wetland Monitoring Program researchers voluntarily participated in a panel of 12 expert researchers to review 13 current H2Ohio Wetland Project proposals in the Western Lake Erie Basin watershed, in response to an Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR) request for assistance. This work fell outside the formal scope of work of the Monitoring Program's priorities under the current award but was considered a beneficial investment for everyone involved. As reviewers, Monitoring Program researchers indicated which proposed Projects would likely retain impactful nutrient loads and noted Project design information requirements necessary to appropriately evaluate proposed Projects. These insights were directly applied to improve the criteria for Project selection and the design of funded Projects. They also supported the establishment of proposal documentation needed to guarantee that relevant information is acquired for future Project proposals.

Presentations, Publications, and Meetings

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program researchers and students presented seven posters and 27 presentations across 16 scientific conferences, management meetings, and departmental seminars in 2024, 12 of which were undergraduate or graduate student research presentations. Additionally, a peer-reviewed manuscript was published by Monitoring Program researchers². Interacting with various disciplines (hydrology, soil science, ecological modeling) allows researchers to bring state of the art science to the Monitoring Program approach for assessment of wetland water quality nutrient function.

Professional Development

Full-time staff are essential to having consistent sampling, informed data processing and summaries, and sustained working relationships with Project property managers and other Monitoring Program partners. Investment in full-time staff is essential for relationship-building with partners, field and lab work capacity, and institutional knowledge for Program resilience.

¹ H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, 2024. *H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: Monitoring Framework*. Kinsman-Costello, L.E., K. Fussell, C. Winslow, J. Kerns, O.F. Schloegel, R. Mendonça, R. Becker, T. Bridgeman, K. Doro, S. J. Jacquemin, L. Johnson, G. Liu, K. McCluney, H. Michaels, W.R. Midden, S. Newell, M. Back, L. Brown, I. Rahman, and Z. Swan. Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN) for the Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR). Columbus, OH, USA.

² Anderson, Kenneth J., Bishwodeep Adhikari, Olivia F. Schloegel, Raissa Marques Mendonca, Michael P. Back, Nicholas Brocato, Jacob A. Cianci-Gaskill, et al. 2024. "We Know Less about Phosphorus Retention in Constructed Wetlands than We Think We Do: A Quantitative Literature Synthesis." *Ecological Indicators* 169 (December):112969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.112969>.

This commitment to full-time staff is also an investment in the future of the wetlands workforce as a whole. Through shared spaces facilitated by the Monitoring Program, such as Partner Day of the Annual Workshop, field and technical staff from the research space and the restoration professional world have the opportunity to learn from one another's realities. An early challenge of the Monitoring Program was a lack of shared language and framing between agency personnel, wetland designers, land managers, and academic researchers. Just a few years later, the 2024 Partner Day saw representatives from each of those groups working together to converge upon a list of relevant wetland features that connect management and restoration approaches with biogeochemical methods to assess accurate nutrient function. This exercise not only served to begin formalizing some of that much-needed shared language but also highlighted that the students and young professionals contributing to these discussions are building cross-disciplinary competency early in their careers. Such investment lays the groundwork to reduce one common barrier, the difference in vocabulary and jargon, to agency- and management-relevant wetland science going forward.

The Monitoring Program also creates mechanisms for students and technical staff to participate frequently in Program-wide settings (e.g., sample design meetings, regional scientific conferences, data synthesis working groups, lab analysis trainings) alongside not only their peers but also more senior researchers, further building confidence and professional competence. This culture of open contribution is evident both in structured Program activities and more informal discussions. Making space for contributions from varied perspectives and experience levels in this manner not only aids early-career professionals in developing peer-to-peer communication skills but also continually strengthens Program-wide facility with the principles of team science that have undergirded the early collaborative successes of the Monitoring Program. The Monitoring Program provides numerous opportunities for graduate and undergraduate students to develop and implement independent research with support of their universities, thus multiplying the workforce development benefits directly supported by state funding to provide formative opportunities for student research.

Appendix

Student Training

The Program has trained 29 undergraduate students across 4 universities, 5 of which have also completed independent student research projects.

Crew Type	University	# of Graduate Students	# of Undergraduate Students
Base	Heidelberg University		2
Base	Kent State University	3	5
Base	Bowling Green State University	4	11
Base	Wright State University		5
Vegetation	Bowling Green State University		6

List of Publications and Presentations

Publications

Anderson, K. J., Adhikari, B., Schloegel, O. F., Mendonça, R. M., Back, M. P., Brocato, N., Cianci-Gaskill, J. A., McMurray, S. E., Bahlai, C., Costello, D. M., & Kinsman-Costello, L. (2024). We know less about phosphorus retention in constructed wetlands than we think we do: A quantitative literature synthesis. *Ecological Indicators*, 169, 112969.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.112969>

Moghtaderi, N. Predicting nitrogen in plant leaves using hyperspectral measurements and machine learning [Unpublished master's thesis] University of Toledo.

Mohammed, I. (2024). Simulating hydrologic complexities of a nutrient-reduction wetland in the Midwest of the United States [Master's thesis, Bowling Green State University]. OhioLINK ETD.
https://etd.ohiolink.edu/acprod/odb_etd/ws/send_file/send?accession=bgsu1715263279441561&disposition=inline

Conference and Management Meeting Presentations

**student presenter*

S. Newell, S. Jacquemin, J. Myers, M. Jutte. January 2024. Assessing Nutrient Load Reductions in H2Ohio Constructed Wetlands: Case Studies from Brooks Park and the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetlands. Great Lakes Seminar Series (CIGLR/GLERL), Online.

L. Johnson, L. Kinsman-Costello. March 2024. H2Ohio Wetlands. Conservation Technology and Tillage Conference, Ada, OH.

W. Midden, M. Stump, M. Mizanur Rahman, S. Faulkner, A. Goetz, A. McGuire Rzicznek, A. Challu, N. Hensley. April 2024. Wetlands: the kidneys of the environment, the habitat of diverse wildlife, the cradles of life. Storytelling and Sustainability Panel for BGSU Earth Month, Bowling Green, OH.

*H. Hoehn. May 2024. Quantifying Primary Algal Groups in H2Ohio Wetlands. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

O. Schloegel. May 2024. Cultivating Science-Policy-Practitioner Partnerships in Wetland Restoration. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

Z. Swan. May 2024. Capitalizing on the Capabilities of Sensor Network Systems in H2Ohio Wetlands. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

W. Midden, C. Kohart, G. Hunt, *L. Busselle, L. Kinsman-Costello. May 2024. Evaluation of the reduction of phosphorus and nitrogen export to the watershed due to creation of geographically isolated wetlands. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

*G. Watson. May 2024. Phosphorus Dynamics in the Sediment of a Lake Erie Coastal Wetland. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

*H. Esber. May 2024. Wetland surface water extent at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project using PyGEE- SWToolbox. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

*K. Peterson. May 2024. What Mud Can Do For You: Soil Removal of Phosphorus from H2Ohio Wetlands. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

L. Kinsman-Costello, R. Becker, T. Bridgeman, K. Doro, S. Jacquemin, L. Johnson, G. Liu, K. McCluney, H. Michaels, W. R. Midden, S. Newell, K. Fussell, C. Winslow, O. Johnson, O. Johnson Raissa Mendonca, E. Saas, J. Kerns. May 2024. Evaluating Nutrient Function Across Diverse Wetland Projects: The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, Ohio, USA. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

*L. Busselle, W. Robert Midden, L. Kinsman-Costello. May 2024. Effects of Some Flow-In/No-Flow-Out Wetland Pools on Phosphorous and Nitrogen Export. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

*M. Back. May 2024. Sediment-surface water nutrient exchange across vegetation patches in a diked Lake Erie wetland. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

S. Newell. May 2024. Assessing Nutrient Load Reductions in H2Ohio Constructed Wetlands: Case Studies from Brooks Park and the Burntwood- Langenkamp Wetlands. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

W. Midden, M. Duhamel, A. Braucksieck, R. Furlong, J. Rife, L. Eggenton, B. Swartz, K. O'Shea, K. Tarallo, C. Kuchle, L. Kinsman-Costello. May 2024. A wetlands project designed for K-12 students to engage in citizen science. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

C. Winslow. May 2024. Ohio's Harmful Algal Bloom Research Initiative: Lessons Learned and Gaps to Address. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

E. Saas. May 2024. The H2Ohio Wetland Restoration & Wetland Monitoring Programs: Managing Wetland Restoration for Water Quality. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

R. Mendonça, I. Rahman, L. Kinsman-Costello. May 2024. Tools and workflows of a data management system for heterogeneous wetland monitoring data. International Association for Great Lakes Research Annual Meeting, Windsor, ON.

B. Adhikari, K. Anderson, C. Bahlai, D. Costello, L. Kinsman-Costello. June 2024. Differences between topographical and hydrological wetland drainage area: implications for estimating wetland functions. Society of Freshwater Science Annual Meeting, Philadelphia, PA.

K. Anderson, B. Adhikari, C. Bahlai, D. Costello, L. Kinsman-Costello, O. Schloegel, R. Marques Mendonça, *M. Back. June 2024. Knowledge gaps in our understanding of phosphorus retention in wetlands: effects of structural features and monitoring approaches on estimates of P retention. Society for Freshwater Science Annual Meeting, Philadelphia, PA.

L. Kinsman-Costello. August 2024. Are Wetlands the Kidneys of The Landscape? The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program. Lake Erie Science and Outdoor Writers Conference, Gibraltar Island, OH.

L. Kinsman-Costello. September 2024. Are Wetlands The Kidneys of the Landscape?: The H2Ohio Wetlands Monitoring Program. Ohio Sea Grant Harmful Algal Blooms State of the Science meeting, Toledo, OH.

L. Kinsman-Costello. September 2024. Are Wetlands the Kidneys of The Landscape? The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program. Ohio Sea Grant Freshwater Sciences Webinar Series, Online.

S. Lee, I. Mohammed, G. Liu, W. Midden, L. Kinsman-Costello, J. Kearns. September 2024. Integrated hydrologic modeling of a recently restored floodplain wetland for reducing nutrients. Geological Society of America Annual Meeting, Anaheim, CA.

*M. Back, L. Kinsman-Costello, S. Newell, *G. Watson, E. Horton, *H. Esber, E. Campbell, J. Myers. October 2024. Sediment-surface water nutrient exchange across vegetation patches in a diked Lake Erie wetland. Great Lakes Coastal Symposium, Rochester, NY.

L. Kinsman-Costello, Z. Swan, L. Skowronek, *M. Back, *G. Watson, R. Becker, T. Bridgeman, K. Doro, S. Jacquemin, L. Johnson, G. Liu, K. McCluney, H. Michaels, W. R. Midden, S. Newell, C. Winslow, O. Schloegel, R. Marques Mendonça, J. Kerns. October 2024. Evaluating Nutrient Function of Coastal Wetland Reconnections and Restorations: The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, Ohio, USA. Great Lakes Coastal Symposium, Rochester, NY.

O. Schloegel, L. Kinsman-Costello, R. Marques Mendonça, J. Kerns, E. Saas, R. DeNoewer. October 2024. Cultivating Science-Policy-Practitioner Partnerships in Wetland Restoration. Great Lakes Coastal Symposium, Rochester, NY.

J. Kerns, L. Kinsman-Costello, E. Saas. October 2024. The H2Ohio Wetland Restoration & Wetland Monitoring Programs: Managing Wetland Restoration for Water Quality. Great Lakes Coastal Symposium, Rochester, NY.

I. Rahman, R. Marques Mendonca. October 2024. Workflow & programmatic implementation of a data management system for heterogeneous wetland monitoring data. Student Professional Development Seminar, Department of Geography and Planning, University of Toledo, Toledo, OH.

D. Dean, R. Becker, N. Moghtaderi. October 2024. Object-Based Classification of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)/Drone Imagery to Monitor H2Ohio Wetlands. Fall Tech Meeting, Eastern Great Lakes Region, American Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (ASPRS), Toledo, OH.

L. Kinsman-Costello. October 2024. Are Wetlands the Kidneys of The Landscape? The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program. Ohio Surface Water Policy Conference, Columbus, OH.

*E. Rettig, A. Nainiger, J. Boehler, L. Johnson. November 2024. What is the Equilibrium Phosphorus Concentration in H2Ohio Wetland Sediments?. Water Management Association of Ohio Annual Meeting and Symposium, Columbus, OH.

J. Dick, *E. Rettig, L. Johnson, J. Boehler, A. Nainiger, E. Clark, D. Jones. November 2024. Vegetation Decomposition and Leaching in H2Ohio Wetlands. Water Management Association of Ohio Annual Meeting and Symposium, Columbus, OH.

I. Rahman, R. Marques Mendonça. December 2024. Implementation of a data management system for heterogeneous wetland monitoring data. LEARN Annual Meeting 2024, Huron, OH

R. Becker, N. Moghadari. December 2024. Using machine learning to predict nitrogen content in plant leaves from hyperspectral Vis-NIR measurements in a restored wetland system in Oakwoods Nature Preserve, Ohio. American Geophysical Union Annual Meeting, Washington, DC.